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Extreme Poverty In The Context Of International Human Rights Law: The Case Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Extreme poverty continues to pose a significant threat to the realization of fundamental human rights globally. In Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation; millions live in conditions of destitution, marked by lack of access to adequate food, clean drinking water, shelter, good healthcare and education. This study examines extreme poverty in Nigeria through the lens of international human rights law, assessing Nigerian's legal obligation and practical responses. Despite numerous normative commitments including the Nigeria's ratification of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, the vast majority of Nigerians live in extreme poverty of \$1.90 per day in 2008 (\$.2.15 in 2024 dollars) living on less than the International Poverty Line (IPL), deprivation of basic human needs including food, clean drinking water, shelter, good healthcare, education and employment. The study analyses the extent to which extreme poverty violates or undermines legally protected human rights. While Nigeria is a signatory to key treaties that recognizes the right to an adequate standard of living, the domestic framework particularly the 1999 Constitution largely classifies socio-economic rights as non-justiciable. This creates a legal vacuum, allowing systemic poverty to persist without enforceable remedies. The study examines the challenges of poverty in Nigeria, including child labor, unemployment, food security, housing deficits, poor access to education and poor healthcare. It evaluates national poverty alleviation programs and critiques the limited effectiveness and policy implementation, judicial enforcement, and social protection. Using a doctrinal and comparative methodology, it argued that Nigeria's continued failure to address extreme poverty constitute violation of human rights and dignity which is a breach of its international obligations. The study undertakes a comparative analysis on how other jurisdictions such as; China, Vietnam, South Africa, Singapore and Finland were able to reduce extreme poverty. The study concludes with recommendations for constitutional reforms, stronger enforcement mechanisms, and the adoption of a human rights-based approach to poverty alleviation, emphasizing dignity, accountability and access to justice.

Keywords: Human Rights, Poverty, Extreme Poverty, International Law, Human Rights Protection, Violation of Human Rights.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Extreme poverty in its most severe form, remains one of the world's most pressing human challenges and it is one of the development concerns. Poverty is not only deprivation of economic or material resources but also a violation of human dignity. International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights¹ provide right to adequate standard of living and general comments on housing, food, clean drinking water. According to the world Bank: Extreme poverty refers to the condition in which individuals live on less than the International Poverty Line (IPL) of \$ 1.90 per day in 2018 (\$.2.15 in 2024 dollars)² lacking access to basic

¹ ICESCR 1966, Article 11 – 13.

² J J McCusker, (1997), *How Much Is That in Real Money? Historical Price Index for Use as a Deflator of Money Values in Economy of the United States.*

necessities for survival. Globally, despite significant progress, millions of people remain trapped in extreme poverty with a disproportionate number residing in Africa. Nigeria, the region's most populous African nation and largest economy, paradoxically holds the grim distinction of housing one of the highest numbers of people living in extreme poverty. Meanwhile same Nigeria is referred to as the giant of Africa. As of 2022, the National Bureau of statistics (NBS)³ reported that approximately 63% of Nigerians are multi-dimensionally poor, lacking in healthcare, education and standard living. Furthermore, in Nigeria, poverty is more acute in rural areas than in urban areas. In the rural areas a significant portion of the poor population uses dung, wood, or charcoal for cooking instead of clean energy and they drink polluted water which in the end endanger their health. The pervasiveness of poverty in Nigeria has profound implications for the enjoyment of basic human rights. Consequently, poor people in Nigeria are vulnerable to various human rights abuses. Therefore, the extreme poor individuals are deprived of adequate food, clean drinking water, shelter, good healthcare and education and, they are excluded from fully participating in society by way of discrimination. Their guaranteed rights under the Nigeria Constitution⁴ are being infringed on a daily basis. Poverty can make anyone to be vulnerable and unstable and, this is one of the root causes of insecurity in Nigeria. What guarantees stability in Nigeria is when human rights are secured. When human rights are denied and/or are subjected to some level of deprivation they become vulnerable to any given situation. Vulnerability in a restricted sense, is when the victim has lost his dignity which exhibits total denial of human rights.⁵ In extreme cases, poverty results in exploitation, child labor, malnutrition, homelessness, and premature death, all which are violations on international human rights standard of living. Human rights are fundamental freedoms and entitlements inherent to every person by virtue of being human. One of the basic factors that can secure peace and poverty alleviate in Nigeria is respect and protection of human rights. The Government of Nigeria should provide basic needs of the people through education, job creation, food, clean drinking water, housing accommodation, good healthcare and infrastructural development which guarantees stability in a civilized nation.

2.0 DEFINITION OF TERMS

2.1 Human Rights

The definition of Human rights and understanding leads to more adequate responses to many facets of poverty in this context. It gives attention to the critical vulnerability and subjective daily assaults and abuses on human dignity that accompany poverty. Importantly, human rights look not just at resources but also at the capabilities, choices, security and power needed for the enjoyment of an adequate standard of living and other fundamental civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights.

Human rights are rights which stand above the ordinary laws of the land and which in fact are antecedent to the political society itself. They are fundamental rights which are inalienable and are not just derived from the constitution; they are inherent in the individual as a human being.⁶

According to Umzurike⁷, human rights are thus; claims, which are invariably supported by law, men of society, especially on his official manager or groups on the basis of their humanity. Following therefore, Igwe: have this to say; "human rights can be seen as cherished entitlement endowed in every person in virtue of being only a human and which are extinguishable even when they are massive, consistent and systematic, as they carry the status innateness, being inherent, inalienable and therefore immutable."⁸ After all, it is always pertinent to be recall that the only reason why state is created or exist in international law is to promote and

³ National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), (17 November 2022). *Nigeria launches its most extensive national measure of multidimensional poverty: The 2022 Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) Survey*. Press Release. Abuja.

⁴ *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999* (as amended), chapter iv.

⁵ O W Igwe, 'LLM and PhD Class Lecture' (Faculty of Law, Rivers State University) at 1pm on Friday 4 April, 2025.

⁶ Kayode Eso definition of human rights in the case of *Ramson Kuti v A.G Federation* (1983) 2 NWLR (pt. 6) 211 at 229 – 230.

⁷ U O Umzurike, "The Present State of Human Rights in Africa", (1986) *Law Journal of Faculty of Law, University of Calabar*; The quote appears in a 2024 lecture (titled "The Nexus Between Political Leadership and Human Rights" delivered by Uwaoma Uche, during which U.O. Umzurike's statement from an earlier work (1986) was cited, at the event of the Human Rights Writers Association of Nigeria (HURIWA), held on 25 July, 2024, in Abuja; his view that human rights are **inherent** (born with individuals), **inalienable** (cannot be taken away), and **imprescriptible** (cannot be lost through time or neglect).

⁸ O W Igwe, *Preliminary Studies in Human Rights Law* (Lagos: Rings & Favolit Ltd., 2002); O W Igwe, 'LLM and PhD Class Lecture' (Faculty of Law, Rivers State University) at 1pm on Friday 22 August, 2025.

protect the rights of her citizens; ideally, the human rights of those person within her territory. We understand that the nature of man is to fulfill his desires which are the basic needs or rights such as food, housing, clothing, clean drinking water, education, employment and so on. Fulfilling all these basic needs of man, conflicts and poverty will be alleviated in Nigeria society.

This brings to mind Rousseau's comments in his book '*Contracte Sociale*'⁹ that "man is born free but everywhere in chains." The theory of social contract presupposes that government owes it a duty to the society to maintain and dispense good governance to the society. Following the social contract theory, chains in the human rights context can be likened to as extreme poverty.

However, one of the most fundamental statements on human rights could be found in the American Declaration of Independence 1776, which states: "We hold these truth to be self-evident that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their creator with certain inalienable rights that among these are life, liberty and the pursuit of happiness."¹⁰

2.2 Poverty

Poverty is a human condition characterized by sustained or chronic deprivation of resources, capabilities, choices, security and power necessary for the enjoyment of an adequate standard of living and other civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights.¹¹

Under international human rights law, poverty can be claimed to the states as the entitlement of the people. Poverty has at least two dimensions. The first is income poverty, which relates to what percentage of a country's population subsists below a minimum level of income or consumption. The second is related to the capability of the poor to come out of poverty in a sustainable manner by having increased access to facilities like food, clean water, good healthcare, housing, education, and employment. Both dimensions required national and international action with bearing in mind that the formulation and implementation of all the policies in the program must be based on a human rights approach maintaining transparency, accountability, participation and non-discrimination with equity in decision making and in sharing the benefits, or in short, through the empowerment of the poor beneficiaries.

2.3 Extreme Poverty

Extreme means suffering from something that is not ordinary or usual; something that is serious or severe.¹² Poverty on the other hand has traditionally been regarded as a phenomenon best understood in terms of income and productivity. Recently, it has more been recognized that poverty is a multi-dimensional problem, extending beyond low income to include physical vulnerability and powerlessness within existing political, judicial and social structures.¹³ Extreme poverty and exclusion from society constitute a violation of human dignity; consequently, the inclusion in national and international plans of measures to eliminate them is a priority.

For the first time, during the celebration of the International day for the Eradication of Poverty, the former Secretary General Kofi Annan clearly stated that poverty is a denial of human rights.¹⁴ The most authoritative definition comes from the United Nations Human Rights Council and the Special Rapporteur on Extreme Poverty and Human Rights: "Extreme poverty is a condition characterized by severe deprivation of basic human needs, including food, safe drinking water, sanitation facilities, health, shelter, education and information. It not only depends on income but also on access to services."¹⁵

⁹ J Rousseau, *The Social Contract or The Principles of Political Rights* (The Knickerbocker Press 1893).

¹⁰ American Declaration of Independence 1776.

¹¹ Declaration by the committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights on Poverty and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (Official Records of the Economic and Social Council, 2002, Supplement No. 2 [E/2002/22-E/C.12/17]. Annex VII), para 8.

¹² A S Hornby, *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* (Oxford University Press: 10th edn 2020).

¹³ A Shephard, (2009). *The Chronic Poverty Report Escaping Poverty Traps*, Chronic Research Centre, <http://www.chronicpoverty.org/uploads/publication_files/CPR2_RaportFull.pdf> (accessed 30 January 2026).

¹⁴ A Sengupta (2006). *Draft Guidelines on a Human Rights Approach to Poverty Reduction* <<http://www.ohchr.org/english/issues/poverty/guidelines/htm>> (accessed 30 January 2026).

¹⁵ *United Nations, Report of the Independence Expert on the Question of Human Rights and Extreme Poverty (A/HRC/7/15, 2008).*

Poverty is described by the United Nations Development Programme¹⁶ as the inability to provide for physical subsistence to the extent of being incapable of protecting human dignity. The office of the high commissioner of human rights drafted the guidelines on human rights approach to poverty reduction. These guidelines include operational directives for a number of specific human rights in the context of poverty such as the right to health, the right to clean drinking water, the right to adequate food, the right to shelter, the right to education, the right to employment and public transport, the right to appear in public without any show of shame, the right to personal security, the right to freedom, civil and political rights, the right to international assistance and cooperation and equal access to justice.

Extreme poverty is in itself a violation of human rights. Fundamental rights are those rights that are inherent in a human being and they are jealously protected by the Constitution. Poverty and denial of access to justice are major obstacles to realization of fundamental rights. More positive actions should be taken by the government in order to prevent or reduce poverty.¹⁷

Igwe stated that poverty is a violation of human rights and that is what makes the poor to be vulnerable.¹⁸ Extreme Poverty constitutes dangerous threats to global existence, as it is the deadliest menace plaguing both developed and underdeveloped nations.¹⁹ Nigeria was ranked the highest in extreme poverty, in June, 2018 globally, and has had to live with a worsening poverty condition, mainly among the rural communities²⁰. As reported by the World Poverty Clock in 2018, Nigeria has the most extreme poor people in the world. According to the report²¹ about 8.9 million Nigerians which represents 50% of the nations estimated 10 million population, lived in extreme poverty. With respect to poverty, the condition of women is even worse. More so, another report²², stated that 70% of poor Nigerians is made up of women. More worrisome is the fact that the vast majority of rural Nigerian women live below survival level. This condition with regard to poverty in the nation remains the same; it is yet to be changed. The most recent Report²³ on this case states that Nigeria still retains the position of Poverty Capital globally. It is worthy to note that, the effect of poverty on women generally mainly indigent and rural women is far – reaching and cannot be over-emphasized. Poverty can be regarded as one of the wheels of progress of violating women. As suggested by Nandi, ‘the frustration associated with poverty can be seen as aggravating aggression and violence against women.’²⁴ Tony –Sampson strongly agrees with the assertion. The United Nations World Summit in September, 2005 tremendously approved the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), and it was decided that all developing countries would provide well-designed national strategies to actualize the MDGs.²⁵ Therefore, it is appropriate to state that there is a direct link between women’s human rights protection and the MDGs. The objectives of the Millennium Development Goals are a progression of eight time-bound improvement objectives that takes a look to resolve issues relating to destitution, instruction, uniformity, wellbeing and climate, to be accomplished

¹⁶ (UNDP 1996). Nigerian Country office, National Human Development Report <<http://www.undp.org>> (accessed 30 January 2026); UNDP (2004). United Nations Development Programme (2004). *Access to justice practice note*; UNDP (2008). United Nations Development Programme (2008). Making the law work for everyone, Report of the Commission on Legal Empowerment of the Poor, United Nations Development Programme, New York.

¹⁷ J Mubangizi, (2007). Poverty production and human rights in the African context, *Law Democracy and Development*, 11, 2; J Mubangizi, (2005). Know your rights: Exploring the connections between human rights and poverty reduction with specific reference to South Africa, 21 *South African J. Human Rights* p. 32.

¹⁸ O W Igwe, ‘LLM and PhD Seminar Class’ (Faculty of Law, Rivers State University) at 1pm on Friday 22 August, 2025.

¹⁹ O M Osinibi, ‘Law as Tool for Poverty Eradication: Need to Enforce Economic Rights in Nigeria’ (1) (1) *Olabisi Onabanjo University Law Journal*. 2009, 48.

²⁰ Yomi Razeem. ‘Nigeria has become the poverty Capital of the World’ <<http://www.qz.cpmAfrica>> Nigeria- (accessed 30 January 2026).

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² A Adepoju, 2004. ‘Feminisation of Poverty in Nigerian Cities: Insights from Focus Group Discussions and Participatory Poverty Assessment.’ *African Population Studies*, vol. 19, Supplements A, pp 141-154. .

²³ B I Rewane. ‘Nigeria Still Poverty Capital of the World’ 6 September, 2021 <<https://www.thisdaylive.com>> (accessed 30 January, 2026).

²⁴ I Nnadi, ‘Eradicating Violence and Gender-Based Violence against Women and Girls – From Rhetoric to Action’. (8)(2). *The Journal of Jurisprudence and Contemporary Issues*, 2016, 41.

²⁵ Osinibi (n 19) 50.

constantly by 2015. They were harmonized by the Global People group at the United Nations Millennium Summit, which took place in New York in September, 2000.²⁶ The first Goal of the MDGs is the eradication of extreme poverty. In Nigeria society the majority of the unemployed and unskilled citizens are mostly women. In various communities, women are totally dependent on the men for survival, as they are not restricted from securing any paying job to satisfy the men's desire or as a result of culture norm. While in other communities, women being bread winners work so hard to meet the needs of the family, thereby forgetting to save for the rainy day or do not have sufficient to save, thereby resulting to increase poverty.

2.4 Human Rights Protection

Human Rights Protection under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)²⁷ establish the universal recognition, promotion, and safeguarding of inherent civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights belonging to all human beings by virtue of their humanity, without discrimination, and the moral obligation placed on states to respect, protect, and promote those rights.

Human Rights Protection under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)²⁸ establish the legal obligation of states parties to progressively realize economic, social, and cultural rights through legislative, administrative, and judicial measures, ensuring minimum core standards necessary for human dignity and social justice.

2.5 Violation of Human Rights

Violation of human rights generally means an act or omission that breaches or infringes on the fundamental rights entitled to all human beings, such as life, liberty, dignity and equality. This breach can be by a state or non-state actor, and includes denial of legal protections, abuse of power, or failure to guarantee basic rights and protections under the law.

3.0 LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

There are combination of national legal policy frameworks and international human rights treaties that provided for the protection of the poor in Nigeria. While the international instruments provide a broad normative foundation, national frameworks are crucial for their implementation and enforcement within the Nigeria context.

3.1 National Frameworks

Nigeria has enacted various national laws and established institutions to address poverty and protect the rights of its poor citizens, drawing inspiration from its international commitments. The 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria contains provisions that, while largely non-justiciable in the form of Fundamental Objectives and Directives Principles of State Policy (Chapter II), lay down the aspiration of a welfare state. These include provisions on economic objectives,²⁹ social objectives³⁰, educational objectives,³¹ and health objectives.³² Although these provisions are generally not enforceable in court, they are intended to guide legislative and executive actions. For instance, section 16(2)(d) states that "the state shall direct its policy towards ensuring that suitable and adequate shelter, suitable and adequate food, reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pensions, and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens."³³

Specific National legislation and policies have been developed to address various aspects of poverty in Nigeria:

3.1.1 National Social Protection Policy (NSPP): Launched in 2017, the NSPP aims to provide a comprehensive framework for social protection interventions in Nigeria. It encompasses social assistance

²⁶ O L Briggs, 'The Direct Link between Women and MDGS' (2) (1) *Empower Magazine*. 2008, 20-21.

²⁷ UDHR 1948, Article 1,2,3-21,22-27 and 28.

²⁸ ICESCR 1966, Article 2(1),6,7,9,11,12, 13 -15.

²⁹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), s 16.

³⁰ *Ibid*, s 17.

³¹ *Ibid*, s 18.

³² *Ibid*, s 17(3)(d).

³³ *Ibid*, s 16(2)(d).

(Example, cash transfer, food assistance), social insurance (example, health insurance, pensions), and labor market interventions (Example, public works programs).³⁴ The policy seeks to reduce poverty and vulnerability, enhance human capital, and promote inclusive growth.

3.1.2 National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP): Established in 2001, NAPEP was a key government aimed at coordinating and implementing poverty reduction programs across various sectors in Nigeria. While its effectiveness has been debated and it has undergone restructuring, it represented a significant effort to address poverty through targeted interventions in areas like youth empowerment, rural development, and social welfare.³⁵

3.1.3 National Health Act: This aims to provide a framework for the regulation, development, and management of a national health system and sets standards for health services. It includes provisions for a Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF) to ensure access to primary healthcare, particularly for vulnerable populations.³⁶

3.1.4 Universal Basic Education (UBE): This Act makes basic education (primary and junior secondary) free and compulsory for all Nigerian children. It aims to improve access to education, especially for children from poor backgrounds, thereby enhancing their future opportunities.³⁷

3.1.5 National Minimum Wage Act: Periodically reviewed, this Act sets the minimum wage for workers in Nigeria, aiming to ensure a living wage and protect low-income earners from exploitation.³⁸

3.1.6 National Social Investment Social Programme (NSIP): Launched in 2016, the NSIP is one of the largest social protection programs in Africa. It includes several components directly targeting the poor and vulnerable:

3.1.7 Condition Cash Transfer (CCT): Provides direct cash transfers to the poorest and most vulnerable households, often with conditions related to school enrolment or health clinic visits.³⁹

3.1.8 Government Enterprise And Empowerment Programme (GEEP): Provides interest free loans to small businesses, traders, and artisans, including market women and youth, to boost economic activities at the grassroots level.⁴⁰

3.1.9 N-Power: A job creation and skills acquisition program for unemployed youth, providing training and stipends in various sectors.⁴¹

3.1.10 National Home Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP): Provides one free meal a day to primary school pupils, aiming to improve nutrition, increase school enrollment, and support local farmers.⁴²

Nigeria has good laws protecting the poor but regrettably, corruption has eaten deep into virtually all the Nigerian's sectors (mostly the politicians in charge) and blocked delivery of basic human-rights needs such as: food, clean drinking water, clothing, shelter, healthcare, education and employment. Monies given for the purpose of alleviation of the poor masses can be diverted and embezzled by a particular circle of politicians to enrich themselves and immediate family members without any empathy and consideration for the poor.

3.2 International Frameworks

Nigeria is a party to numerous treaties but for the purpose of this discourse we shall stream line our discussion to three international instruments: The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁴³, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)⁴⁴ and the African Charter on

³⁴ Nigeria Social Protection Policy (Federal Ministry of Budget and National Planning), 2017.

³⁵ National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), 2001.

³⁶ National Health Act 2014 (Federal Ministry of Health).

³⁷ Universal Basic Education Act 2004. (Federal Ministry of Education).

³⁸ National Minimum Wage (Amendment) Act 2024 (International Labour Organization (ILO) – NATLEX).

³⁹ Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) Programme. (National Social Investment Programme Agency (NSIP) Act, 2023).

⁴⁰ Government Enterprise and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) 2016. (National Social Investment Programme (NSIP)).

⁴¹ N-Power Programme, 2016 (as part of National Social Investment Programme Agency (NSIP) Act 2023) to address youth unemployment and provide skill acquisition opportunities. The program began paying beneficiaries starting in December, 2016.

⁴² National Home Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP). (National Social Investment Programme (NSIP)).

⁴³ UDHR 1948.

⁴⁴ ICESCR 1966.

Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR)⁴⁵ – which establish a comprehensive set of rights that are directly relevant to the protection and upliftment of the poor.

3.2.1 UDHR

Universal Declaration on Human Rights 1948 (UDHR) serves as a foundational document for international human rights law. While not a legally binding treaty in itself, its principles have been widely accepted and have influenced numerous subsequent treaties and national constitutions. The Article relevant to the poor include Article 22, which states that everyone has the right to social security; Article 23 is concerning the right to work, just and favorable conditions of work, and protection against unemployment, Article 25, which recognizes the right to standard of adequate living for the health and well-being of oneself and of one's family, including food, clothing, housing, and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event on unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond one's control; and Article 26 is on the right to education. These provisions lay the groundwork for understanding poverty as a human rights issue, emphasizing the state's responsibility to ensure basic necessities and opportunities for all.

3.2.2 ICESCR

International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966 (ICESCR) was adopted in 1966 and ratified by Nigeria in 1993, this instrument is a legally binding treaty that elaborates on many of the economic, social and cultural rights outlined in the UDHR. Key articles directly impacting the poor include right to work⁴⁶, right to just and favorable conditions of work⁴⁷, right to social security⁴⁸, right to an adequate standard of living, including adequate food, clothing, and housing, and the continues improvement of living conditions⁴⁹, and right to the highest attainable standard of physical and mental health.⁵⁰ The ICESCR places an obligation on state parties to take steps to the maximum of their available resources with a view to achieving progressively the full realization of these rights. This “progressive realization” clause is particularly relevant for developing countries like Nigeria, acknowledging resource constraints while still demanding continuous effort towards fulfilling these rights.⁵¹ Despite this legal frameworks, enforcement and/or implementation remains a significant challenge due to socioeconomic factors, cultural practices, and lack of adequate monitoring mechanisms, particularly in rural areas of Nigeria.

3.2.3 ACHPR

African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights 1981 (ACHPR) was adopted in 1981 and ratified by Nigeria in 1983, is a regional human rights instrument that uniquely incorporates both individual and collective rights, including “peoples' rights.” The ACHPR, unlike the ICESCR, does not explicitly separate economic, social, and cultural rights from civil and political rights, treating them as interdependent and indivisible. Articles relevant to the poor include right to property⁵², right to work under equitable and satisfactory conditions⁵³, right to enjoy the best attainable state of physical and mental health⁵⁴, right to education⁵⁵, and right to economic, social and cultural development.⁵⁶ The ACHPR's emphasis on duties of individuals and the state, as well as its recognition of “peoples' rights” such as the right to development, provides a unique framework for addressing systematic poverty and inequality within an African context. The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights, established under the Charter, monitors its implementation and has developed jurisprudence relevant to

⁴⁵ ACHPR 1981.

⁴⁶ ICESCR 1966, Article 6.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*, Article 7.

⁴⁸ *Ibid*, Article 9.

⁴⁹ *Ibid*, Article 11.

⁵⁰ *Ibid*, Article 12.

⁵¹ Ratification Status for Nigeria. (OHCHR).

⁵² ACHPR 1981, Article 14; Ratification Status for Nigeria. (African Union).

⁵³ *Ibid*, Article 15.

⁵⁴ *Ibid*, Article 16.

⁵⁵ *Ibid*, Article 17.

⁵⁶ *Ibid*, Article 22.

economic and social rights, including cases related to forced evictions and access to essential services.⁵⁷ Regrettably despite these frameworks, challenges in Nigeria still persist, including issues of implementation, corruption, inadequate funding, and the vast scale of poverty. The effectiveness of these national frameworks often depends on political will, institutional capacity, and sustained commitment to human rights principles. The combination of national legal policy and international human rights instruments provides a multifaceted approach to promote and protect the poor in Nigeria, though significant gaps remain in their full realization and enforcement and they are:

1. Lack of Domestic Justiciability and Enforcement of Socio-Economic Rights

Non-justiciability of economic and social rights under the Nigeria Constitution⁵⁸, significantly limits enforcement. For example, the right to health enshrined in Article 12 of the ICESCR cannot be litigated in Nigeria courts due to this clause, weakening accountability mechanisms. Courts are yet to fully embrace the inter-dependency of civil-political and socioeconomic rights in their jurisprudence. The absence of domestication of Nigeria's international commitments such as the ICESCR or UN Charter⁵⁹ rights to food and an adequate standard of living-means these remain 'persuasive' rather than binding in domestic litigation.

2. Fragmented Legal Frameworks without Human Rights Anchoring

Although social protection and poverty reduction schemes exist in Nigeria but they lack a clear human rights-based legal foundation. For example, the COVID 19 era social assistance measures highlighted the need for legislative recreation of the right to social security, yet such legal status lack binding effect domestically. Despite frameworks like the National Health Act 2014 on its basic healthcare provision fund, the constitutional backing for enforceability of health services remains weak and largely symbolic.

3. Institutional Weakness

Nigeria's human rights institutional framework is described as weak and ineffective, especially for rural populations: over 75% of whom lack access to food, clean drinking water, shelter, education and employment and so on. Majority of them lack access to legal representation, and many are unaware of the law to seek redress due to lack of education which ordinarily is supposed to be made free for all by the government. Criminal justice services such as mass pre-trial detention and weaponization of criminal processes continue to disproportionately affect the poor, with reforms ACJA⁶⁰ under enforced. A major deficiency in the development of human rights is one of enforcement. Since the enforcement of human rights largely depends on the domestic machinery of national governments, Nigeria has erected seemingly firm institutional infrastructure to safeguard human rights in the country. The institutional infrastructure includes the judiciary,⁶¹ the National Human Rights Commission,⁶² the Public Complaints Commission,⁶³ and the Legal Aid Council.⁶⁴ Unfortunately, the various institutional mechanisms are not strong enough or capable of providing adequate and effective platforms for meaningful human rights promotion and protection. This is especially so because many of these institutional mechanisms are not independent and do not have the financial and logistical capability to meaningfully function as they ought to.

4. Insufficient Social Protection and Coverage

Only 11% of Nigerians are covered by any form of social protection. The country lacks a well-functioning, universal social security system to shield the poor from economic shocks such as unemployment, sickness, or childbirth. The National Bureau of Statistic estimate that 133 million Nigerians live in multi-dimensional poverty, suffering deprivations, in sanitation, healthcare, food, and housing, yet the legal response remains inadequate.

⁵⁷ For more information on human rights treaties within states' legal and political systems, see Henry J. Steiner et. al., *International Human Rights in Context: Law, Politics, Morals 725-729* (1st edn 1996) at 709.

⁵⁸ *CFRN* (n 29), s 6(6)(c).

⁵⁹ United Nations Charter 1945.

⁶⁰ Administration of Criminal Justice Act 2015.

⁶¹ *CFRN* (n 29) s 6.

⁶² Established pursuant to the National Human Rights Commission Act, (2004) Cap. 46. *LFN*.

⁶³ Established by the Public Complaints Commission Act, (2004) Cap. 37 *LFN*

⁶⁴ Established under the Legal Aid Act, (2004) Cap. L9 *LFN*

5. Poverty as Barrier to Human Rights Protection

The National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) has explicitly recognized that, poverty impedes the realization of fundamental rights, including adequate living standards, health, and education. Yet the integration of poverty considerations into human rights law enforcement is limited.

6. Weak Institutional Capacity and Pro-poor Legal Empowerment

Child domestic workers, many forced into child labor due to poverty, remain poorly protected. The existing institutional mechanisms, despite legal frameworks like the child Rights Act and Children's Charter – Lack capacity, funding, and political will to safeguard such vulnerable groups. Broader efforts at legal empowerment, such as increasing awareness among the poor and enabling access to legal services, remain embryonic and underfunded.

4.0 INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORKS

4.1 The Judiciary

The Judiciary of Nigeria is the primary institution responsible for interpreting and enforcing human rights guaranteed under chapter iv of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act which provides remedies where socio-economic rights violations contribute to extreme poverty. The Judiciary ensures rule of law, protection of rights, and access to justice, especially where government policies or actions worsen poverty conditions.

4.2 National Human Rights Commission (NHRC)

The National Human Rights Commission was established by the National Human Rights Commission Act 1995. The commission addresses issues such as economic deprivation, discrimination, poor access to education, healthcare, and housing which are factors contributing to extreme poverty.

4.3 Pubic Complaints Commissions (PCC)

The Commission addresses administrative injustice and corruption, the Commission helps ensure that government services and social welfare programs reach citizens, particularly the poor.

4.4 Legal Aid Council of Nigeria

The Legal Aid Council of Nigeria provides free legal services to indigent persons both in criminal and certain civil matters. Poor individual often cannot afford legal representation. The Council ensures that poverty does not prevent citizens from enforcing their rights in court.

4.5 The African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights

The Charter is domesticated in Nigeria through the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, making it enforceable in Nigeria courts. The Commission monitors state compliance with the charter. Receives communications (Complaints) on human rights violations and issues recommendations to states including Nigeria.

5.0 CHALLENGES OF POVERTY IN NIGERIA

There are many factors that are attributing to the high rate of poverty in Nigeria. But for the purpose of this study, we shall stream line the challenges to five basic root causes of poverty in Nigeria and they are:

5.1 Child Labour

Poverty forces many children into child labor, preventing them from gaining education and skills necessary for future success. Child labour violates the fundamental rights of children, including the right to education, good healthcare, protection, and a safe childhood as recognized in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, the African Charter on the Rights and welfare of the child and Nigeria's Child Rights Act.⁶⁵ Instead of being in school, many children are pushed into the street hawking, doing domestic work, farming, mining, or menial jobs. This denies them equal opportunities and traps them in

⁶⁵ Child's Rights Act 2003, *Laws of the Federation of Nigeria*: Available at: <https://www.lawhub.com.ng/childs-rights-act-2003/> (accessed 4 March 2026); N S Okogbule, "Combating the 'New Slavery' in Nigeria: An Appraisal of Legal and Policy Responses to Human Trafficking", *Journal of African Law* (cited in 2024 literature); and related papers on human trafficking and child exploitation. journals.sabauni.edu.ge/David Publishing Company; O W Igwe, *Human-Rights Framing of Poverty and Exclusion* (2019).

cycles of poverty - exposing them to hazards, exploitation, and health risks. Poverty is one of the biggest driver of child labour in Nigeria. Many families depend on children's earning to survive.⁶⁶ When parents are unemployed or underpaid, children are forced to support household income. Poor access to affordable education, especially in the rural and conflict-affected areas worsen the problem. The Child's Rights Act is the principal legislation in Nigeria that consolidates the rights of children and aligns with international instruments like the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child. One of the key protections under this law is the prohibition of child labour. Under the Act⁶⁷, it is expressly prohibited for a child to be subjected to any form of exploitative labour. The law defines exploitative labour as work that deprives the child of his or her health, education or development. Furthermore, it sets the minimum age for employment at 18 years and criminalizes the use of children in hazardous work, domestic servitude, or any employment that is mentally, physically, socially, or morally dangerous. The law provides sanctions for violators, including imprisonment and fines, aiming to deter the exploitation of children in both formal and informal sectors. It also mandates the government to implement policies that protect children from economic exploitation and ensure access to free and compulsory basic education for all as a preventive measure.

5.2 Unemployment

Unemployment remains one of the most pressing causes of poverty in Nigeria. Millions of graduates and school leavers cannot secure decent jobs due to limited industries, low economic diversification, and inadequate infrastructure. With fewer income opportunities, families struggle to meet basic needs, leading to widespread poverty. Youth unemployment in particular fuels social unrest and pushes many into informal, low-paying jobs.⁶⁸

5.3 Food Insecurity

Despite Nigeria's vast arable land and agricultural potential, food insecurity is a growing problem. Poor agricultural policies, post-harvest losses, insecurity in farming regions, and dependence on imported food contribute to shortages and high food prices. When households spend most of their income on food, little remains for healthcare, education, or shelter, trapping families in a cycle of poverty and malnutrition.⁶⁹

5.4 Housing Deficit

Nigeria faces an estimated housing deficit of over 20 million units. Rapid urbanization, high construction costs, and weak mortgage systems make affordable housing inaccessible to low-income earners. Many families are forced to live in slums or overcrowded settlements without clean water, electricity, or sanitation, which not only lowers living standards but also perpetuates poverty by affecting health and productivity.⁷⁰

5.5 Poor Access to Education

Education is a key driver of economic mobility, but millions of Nigerian children remain out of school, especially in rural and conflict-affected areas. Factors such as poverty, inadequate infrastructure, teacher shortages, and gender discrimination limit access to quality education. Without skills and knowledge, individuals face limited employment opportunities, which increases the cycle of generational poverty.⁷¹

⁶⁶ A T Adeoti, "Child Labour in Nigeria: Causes and Consequences for National Development", *Kennesaw Journal of Diplomatic and International Relations* 3, no. 1 (2021), <<https://digitalcommons.kennesaw.edu/yajlod/vol3/iss1/7>> (accessed 30 January 2026).

⁶⁷ Child's Rights Act (n 65) Ss 29 - 31.

⁶⁸ World Bank / poverty trend & regional analysis on Nigeria; Niger-Delta social/legal context and unemployment discussion: J Lain., et al., *Estimating a Poverty Trend for Nigeria between 2009 and 2019* (IARIW / World Bank materials), 2022. iariw.org; N S Okogbule, *An Appraisal of the Social-Legal Dynamics of Conflicts in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria*, Int. J. Adv. Multidisc. Res. Stud., 2024. multiresearchjournal.com.

⁶⁹ Food insecurity, agricultural problems, and human-rights framing of poverty: World Bank (Nigeria poverty & NLSS background), *A Better Future for All Nigerians*, (poverty/consumption discussion, NLSS 2018/19). World Bank; O W Igwe, "Poverty and exclusion in Nigeria: from basic needs to millennium development goals — the role of human rights law", MedCrave / ResearchGate, 2019. MedCrave.

⁷⁰ Housing deficit and urbanization: World Bank (poverty and welfare, NLSS material, urban pressures). World Bank; N S Okogbule, writings on Niger Delta deprivation and inequality (see 2024 appraisal). multiresearchjournal.com.

⁷¹ Education and social protection (conditional cash transfers): I S Umezurike, "The Latin American and Nigerian Conditional Cash Transfer Experience: A Comparative Analysis", *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 2020 (online pub. Jul

5.6 Poor Healthcare System

Nigeria's health system suffers from chronic under-funding, weak infrastructure, severe workforce shortages, corruption and inequitable access. Those system failures translate directly into violations of the right to health and related human rights (life, non-discrimination, freedom from cruel/inhuman treatment), because large sections of the population cannot obtain essential, timely, affordable healthcare. High maternal and child mortality rates shows that many women and children fail to receive basic, life-saving care when needed – a classic failure to realize the right to health. Clinical causes (hemorrhage, eclampsia, unsafe abortion, obstructed labour) are treatable but deaths persist because services are unavailable, unaffordable, or unreliable.⁷² The extremely poor are “unable to access good health care” in child and maternal mortality in Nigeria. Poverty is an affliction that only the victim can express⁷³ particularly when its concerns health challenges.

6.0 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF POVERTY ALLEVIATION WITH OTHER JURISDICTIONS:

The honest truth is that no country has literally erased poverty in its entirety. But to a reasonable extent several countries have effectively **eliminated extreme poverty** (the World Bank's \$1.90/day or similar poverty-line thresholds) or driven national poverty rates down from majority to single digits. Below are five success stories - China, Vietnam, South Africa, Singapore and Finland and, explain *how* each achieved major poverty reduction.

6.1 China

Beginning with the 1978 reforms and opening to trade and private enterprise, China sustained very high growth for decades; this growth (manufacturing expansion, urban jobs and migration) lifted nearly 800 million people out of extreme poverty. In the 2010s the Chinese government combined growth with targeted, large-scale poverty-alleviation campaigns (rural development, infrastructure, relocation for some extremely remote households) and declared the eradication of extreme poverty in 2020. There was rapid income gains increased capabilities (health, schooling, housing) at massive scale, expanding real freedoms (capabilities) is central to reducing poverty. But scholars also caution that redistribution, non-discrimination and voice remain necessary to make gains equitable and durable.⁷⁴

6.2 Vietnam

Vietnam's Doi Moi reforms (late 1980s) liberalized agriculture and trade, producing strong rural productivity gains and export growth. The country paired growth with targeted social programs, investments in health and education, and large-scale poverty-targeting (cash transfers, subsidies, nutrition and health outreach). By the 2010s Vietnam pushed extreme poverty below single digits (World Bank reporting shows very large declines; <4% on some lines by 2023). Vietnam's example shows how combining pro-poor growth with public services and targeted social protection can realize socio-economic rights (education, health, adequate standards of living) for large numbers. Scholars in social-rights jurisprudence emphasize that institutional design for social goods matters for justiciability and accountability.⁷⁵

15, 2020). — examines CCTs as social protection to keep children in school and the implementation constraints in Nigeria. [ResearchGate](#); World Bank / NLSS background on consumption, welfare and education linkages. [World Bank](#).

⁷² O Olonade, (2019), Maternal Mortality and Maternal Health Care in Nigeria: Implications for Socio-Economic Development. *International Journal/PMC Articles*.

⁷³ O W Igwe, R I Ahiakwo, & N O Princewill, Poverty and exclusion in Nigeria: From basic needs to millennium development goals – the role of human rights law, *Forensic Research & Criminology International Journal*, (2019) 7 (4): 147 – 152.

⁷⁴ L Zhang, et al. (2023) “The impact of the Anti-Poverty Relocation Program in China.” *Resources and Energy Economics*, 73, 101396; X Li, & L Li, (2021) “Evaluation of China's Targeted Poverty Alleviation Policies: A Decomposition Analysis.” *Sustainability*, 13(21), 11691.

⁷⁵ M Ramla (2023), *Poverty Reduction Comparative Perspective: Models and Lessons for Viet Nam*. UNDP; V H Tran, & Q T Pham, “Growth and poverty reduction in Vietnam: A strategic policy modelling study.” *National Accounting Review*, 6(3), 449-464.

6.3 South Africa

South Africa's 1996 Constitution guarantees rights to social security, housing, food, clean drinking water and health and requires the state to take reasonable measures (progressive realization) mandated to create a human rights foundation for anti-poverty.⁷⁶ Extreme poverty is reduced mainly by building a constitutional, right based social protection system and by explaining cash grants and basic services – these measures substantially cut extreme poverty but, without robust job creation and deeper structural reforms, large-scale poverty and inequality persist.⁷⁷

6.4 Singapore

Singapore combined rapid, sustained economic growth with deliberate social policies: state-led housing (HDB public housing that reaches most citizens), active labour and skills policies, and targeted cash/social assistance (ComCare and other schemes). These policies have kept extreme material deprivation rare for citizens even while the city-state manages cost-of-living pressures. Singapore's social-support reporting shows declining numbers in need of short-term assistance and strong housing coverage. Singapore shows how pairing universal/near-universal public goods (affordable housing, basic services) with labour-market inclusion prevents severe deprivation and supports dignity — consistent with a rights-based emphasis on both entitlements and effective delivery. But scholars would still press for transparency, non-discrimination and participation in program design.⁷⁸

6.5 Finland

Finland is often used as a Nordic example where strong welfare institutions and universal social policies (especially free education) have pushed poverty to some of the lowest rates in the world. Finland reduced extreme poverty through the following ways:

6.5.1 Universal welfare state model: Finland built a “Nordic welfare model” after World War II, based on *universalism* (everyone is entitled), progressive taxation, and comprehensive social security. This reduced inequality and poverty across the life cycle (childhood, unemployment, old age).⁷⁹

6.5.2 Social protection system: Includes universal child allowances, housing support, unemployment insurance, minimum pensions, and universal healthcare. According to the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), these transfers reduce poverty rates by more than half compared with market incomes.⁸⁰

6.5.3 Labour market policies: Active labour-market programs, collective bargaining, and minimum protections ensured fewer “working poor.” Finland effectively eliminated *extreme poverty* (no population group lives under the World Bank \$2.15/day line).⁸¹

6.5.4 Constitutional right: Section 16 of the *Finnish Constitution* guarantees everyone the right to basic education free of charge. It also obliges public authorities to secure equal educational opportunities beyond the compulsory level.⁸²

6.5.5 Universal free system: All levels of education from pre-primary to doctoral studies are free of tuition. Textbooks, meals, transport, and materials are publicly funded at the basic-education level. Universities are tuition-free for EU/EEA citizens; since 2017, non-EU students may pay fees, but scholarships exist.⁸³

⁷⁶ Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996, chapter 2, Bill of Rights, sections 26 and 27.

⁷⁷ S Liebenberg, (2023), *Applying a human rights lens to poverty and economic inequality: The Experience of South Africa* Human Rights Commission. *Sage Journals*.

⁷⁸ C Lim, et al (2016) “Housing as a Social Determinant of Health in Singapore.” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 13(12), 1156.

⁷⁹ T Pekkarinen, et al. (2017). “Equality of Opportunity and the Finnish Comprehensive School.” *Journal of Public Economics; S* Fredman, (2008). *Human Rights Transformed: Positive Rights and Positive Duties*. OUP; P Alston, (2019). UN Report of the Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty, A/HRC/41/39; M Langford, (2008). *Social Rights Jurisprudence: Emerging Trends in International and Comparative Law*. Cambridge UP.

⁸⁰ OECD, “Finland: Income Inequality and Poverty Indicators” (2022). Data showing redistribution impact.

⁸¹ A Sen, (1999). *Development as Freedom*. Oxford University Press.

⁸² Constitution of Finland (1999, amended): section 16 on education rights.

⁸³ Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture, “Education system in Finland” (2023). Overview of free access and equality measures.

6.5.6 Equality measures: The system deliberately reduces stratification (comprehensive schools, no early tracking, and support for weaker students). This reflects a rights-based commitment to equality and non-discrimination in education.

7.0 CONCLUSION

Extreme poverty in Nigeria remains one of the most urgent human rights challenges of the 21st century. International Human Rights Law, particularly through instruments such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR, 1948), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 1966), and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (1981), recognizes the right to an adequate standard of living, food, clean drinking water, education, housing, and social security. Nigeria, as a signatory to these treaties, bears both legal and moral obligations to ensure that poverty is reduced and citizens live in dignity and non-discrimination. However, widespread child labor, unemployment, food insecurity, inadequate housing, limited access to quality education, weak healthcare, poor governance and corruption has continue to exacerbate the poverty situation. Poverty in Nigeria is not merely an economic issue but a violation of fundamental human rights, denying millions the opportunity to live in dignity, participate in society, and exercise their freedoms. Thus, tackling poverty in Nigeria requires a rights-based approach, where state policies and interventions prioritize human dignity, equality, accountability, and social justice in line with international obligations.

8.0 RECOMMENDATION

1. Nigeria should adopt a Human Rights-Based Approach to Poverty Reduction: Nigeria government must frame poverty eradication policies not only as economic reforms but as obligations under international human rights law. This includes integrating rights to food, clean drinking water, housing, good healthcare, and education into national development strategies.
2. Nigeria government should implement agricultural reforms to enhance food production, reduce import dependence, and subsidize small-scale farmers. Government should regulate the high cost accommodation at all level in the country and establish affordable housing policies that prioritize low-income families, ensuring that housing is treated as a human right obligation.
3. Nigerian government should expand decent job opportunities through industrial diversification, agricultural modernization, and digital economy investments. Introduce comprehensive social protection schemes such as unemployment benefits, child support, and old-age pensions, ensuring no Nigerian falls below a minimum standard of living across the nation.
4. Nigeria government should adopt the Finland system of education as a tool for poverty eradication. There should be guarantee free, compulsory, and quality primary and secondary education, with special focus on rural communities. Expand vocational and technical training to equip youths with employable skills.
5. Nigeria government should strengthen the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) and expand coverage to vulnerable groups. Invest in rural health infrastructure to ensure universal access to essential healthcare. Policies must focus on marginalized groups (women, children, persons with disabilities, and rural populations) who are disproportionately affected by poverty. Implement gender-sensitive budgeting to close inequality gaps.